

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

D5.3 Communication and dissemination report v2.0

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ACRONYMS LIST

D&C	Dissemination and Communication
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This final version of D5.3 presents all the communication and dissemination activities performed within the second year of the GOhydro project and provides an overview of all such activities realized within the lifetime of the project. All activities are described and most importantly assessed with respect to the KPIs set by the communication and dissemination plan (D5.2).

1 INTRODUCTION

GOhydro had set in its work plan a work package dedicated to the planning and execution of broad communication and dissemination activities (D&C) with the intent maximise the outreach and impact of the project. Taking into account the innovativeness of the project's proposed solution and, thus, its relative need to mature beyond the scope of the project, GOhydro identified three strategic directions the D&C activities should take:

- (1) Raising public awareness and ensuring maximum visibility of the project key facts, outputs and findings amongst the public;
- (2) Supporting the transfer of project results and engagement from key stakeholders in academia and industry;
- (3) Enhancing the commercial potential of the results and users' reception.

Towards that purpose a specific dissemination and communication plan was set in place at M6 of the project (D5.2), while well-defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were set even at the stage of proposal writing for the consortium to have a credible and measurable toolkit to assess and evaluate the impact of the GOhydro communication and dissemination strategy. Therefore, this deliverable not only enlists the D&C activities of Year 2 of the project, but also evaluates the success of the D&C plan implementation in terms of the KPIs.

The deliverable is separated into 3 sections. The first section re-iterates the major goals and means to achieve them as set in the dissemination strategy (described in detail in D5.2). The second part compiles all the actions realized within the 2nd year of the project. In the final section of D5.3, all activities realized within the lifetime of GOhydro are presented with respect to the KPIs and an overall assessment of the D&C plan effectiveness is performed. The Annexes that can be found at the end of this document contain the details with regards to social media presence of the GOhydro project.

2 SUMMARY OF THE GOHYDRO D&C PLAN

The D&C plan was based on the AIDA concept (Rawal, 2013) and its variations according to which an efficient plan should identify four hierarchical and sequential stages that culminate to stakeholder engagement. These are:

1. **Awareness:** refers to the creation and promotion of the GOhydro identity that will be able to establish itself as a standard imagery evocating the project’s concept and scope;
2. **Interest:** refers to the means used to communicate and highlight the added value of the GOhydro solutions in a way that raises the interest of targeted audiences;
3. **Desire:** deals with the modalities through which audiences will be motivated to test the GOhydro solutions and actively participate in its ecosystem;
4. **Action:** incorporates the strategic steps for transforming knowledge, interest and motivation into active engagement, either as part of a growing GOhydro community or as part of a client base.

Based on the AIDA fundamental concept, but taking into account the particular character and objectives of the project, the GOhydro consortium compiled a concrete D&C plan spanning across all four AIDA axes. The plan was construed in order to effectively spread the GOhydro message to the relevant communities and defined the following KPIs (Table 1.1). All details about the channels, measures and actions may be found in D5.2.

Table 1 Channels of Communication and Dissemination and their relative KPIs and Targeted Values

Channel Name	KPI	Targeted Value (Year 1)	Targeted Value (Year 2) ¹
GOhydro website	Visits	≥1,000	≥2,000
	Downloads	50	≥250
	Newsletter subscribers	≥100	≥200
GOhydro social media	Tweets	20	≥100
	Twitter Followers	50	≥300
	LinkedIn Page Members	50	≥100
	Research Gate Followers	10	≥50
	You tube Videos	-	≥2
Scientific publications	Journal Publications	1	≥4
	Conference Proceedings	2	≥6
Press relations	Newspaper/Magazine Articles	1	≥4
	Interviews and Presentations	1	≥2
Event participation	Scientific Conferences/Workshops	4	>12
	Industry Events	1	>4
	Number of young students attending NCSR-D educational programme in urban farming	100	>300

¹ Accumulated value.

3 YEAR 2 D&C ACTIVITIES

The D&C activities realized during Year 2 are per category:

Project Website
<p>The project website, https://www.gohydro.org/ has been up and running since the first days of the project and will be maintained for at least two years after the project’s completion. The website includes a public area through which public information is disseminated, as well as a private area for the distribution of information restricted to the consortium. Particular attention has been paid to make the site appealing to the visitors, while including all relevant content, and to match to the logo and to the “colour branding” of the project. The site regularly features posts about tweets and news as well as the first presentations of the project. The site was continuously updated with news and results of the project</p>

Social Media Presence
<p>According to the Dissemination and Communication Plan, it was deemed very important for the project’s visibility to create social media accounts. In addition, it was opted to disseminate public project deliverables and publications via Zenodo. Throughout Year 2 numerous posts were created in all accounts up until the last “official” date of the project. All screenshots within this table are from the latest posts all accounts (February 2022). The complete list of all posts in Twitter and LinkedIn alongside their impression can be found in Annex II.</p>

Twitter	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu	
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/gohydro/	

<p>Slideshare</p>	<p>https://www.slideshare.net/GOhydro/Project</p>	
<p>YouTube Channel</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCPhjbcI3JHsHCdjeaz-G_yQ</p>	
<p>ResearchGate</p>	<p>https://www.researchgate.net/project/GOHYDRO</p>	
<p>Zenodo Community</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/communities/gohydro/</p>	

Scientific Publications						
Within Year 2 there had been 3 scientific publications, while 4 more based on the project results are currently being prepared or submitted pending review/publication						
Authors	Title	Publication Type	Publication Venue	Publisher	Publication Status	Year Published
P.I. Moraru, Rusu, T., O.S. Mintas	Trial Protocol for Evaluating Platforms for Growing Microgreens in Hydroponic Conditions	Journal paper	Foods 2022, 11(9), Article number 1327; https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11091327	MDPI	Published	3 May 2022
Rusu, T.; Moraru, P.I.	Parameters monitored in order to improve the performance of microgreen production in hydroponic platforms	Conference paper	Agro International Conference on Agriculture, June 04-06, 2022	Azerbaijan State Agrar University	Published	June 04-06, 2022

Moraru, P.I., T. Rusu	Trial protocol for evaluating platforms for growing microgreens in hydroponic conditions	Conference paper	The 21st International Conference "Life Sciences for Sustainable Development", p. 18, 15th-17th September 2022	USAMV Cluj-Napoca, Romania	Published	September 15-17, 2022
Cowden, R.J., Markussen, B., Ghaley, B.B.	Quantifying the Impact of Light Spectra of Programmable LEDs for Microgreen Biomass and Secondary Metabolite Production in Controlled Environment Agriculture using Multilinear Regression Models	Journal paper	Journal of Plant Nutrition, Frontiers in Nutrition, or Plant Foods For Human Nutrition	TBD	In Progress	TBD
Cowden, R.J., Markussen, B., Ghaley, B.B.	The Impact of Light Spectrum and Intensity, Seeding Density, and Fertilization on Biomass and Secondary Metabolite Accumulation in Four Species of Brassicaceae Microgreens	Journal paper	Horticulturae (MDPI), Agronomy (MDPI), PLOS ONE, or BIOLOGY, or Frontiers in Plant Science	TBD	In Progress	TBD
Rusu, T. Moraru, P.I., Mintas, O.S., Carbanar, M.M.	Basil and Lettuce Microgreens Production in Low-Cost Hydroponic Installations, under Operational and Semi-Controlled Conditions	Journal paper	Sustainability	MDPI	In Progress	2023
K. Misiakos , A. Christofi, G. Margariti, A. Salapatas , P.Zervas, P. Karampimperis, P. Tarantillis, E. H. Kaparakou and E. Makarona	Determining the nutrient content of hydroponically-cultivated microgreens with immersible silicon photonic sensors: a pre-liminary study	Journal Paper	Sensors – Special issue „Optical Sensors Technology and Applications: Part B“	MDPI	Manuscript under preparation	2023

Publications in Magazines and Daily Press					
Date of the Publication	Title of the publication	Vehicle of the publication	URL where the publication can be accessed	Online article, printed article, newsletter, other	Partner leading the work/publication
July 2022	Partnership between Wikifarmer and GOhydro	Wikifarm site	https://wikifarmer.com/partnership-between-wikifarmer-and-gohydro/	Blogpost	SCiO

Event Participation (including Scientific Conferences)								
Event Name	Event URL	Lead Partner	Event Type	Nature of Contribution	Location	Date(s)	Audience	Number of Participants
"AI for Industry and Business" online event organized by the Hellenic Federation of Enterprises	https://tinyurl.com/mrmy5s3	SCiO	Industry event	Presentation	virtual	virtual	23-03-2022	Industry
Agro International Conference on Agriculture	-	USA MV	Conference	Presentation	virtual	virtual	04.06.2022-06.06.2022	Research
85th Thessaloniki International Fair	https://thessalonikifair.gr/en	SCiO	Trade Fair	Booth	Thessaloniki	Greece	16/9/2022 - 19/9/2022	Research, Governmental Agencies, Industry
CivTech Alliance Global Scale-up Programme 2, Challenge 2: Green Public Procurement, Tech Online Day	-	SCiO	Industry event	Presentation	virtual	virtual	21-10-2022	Industry
A novel biosensing platform of directly-immersible silicon photonic probes for applications at the point of interest	https://www.mne2022.org/	NCS R-D	Conference	Presentation	Leuven	Belgium	19/9/2022-23/9/2022	Research
International Horticultural Congress	Home page - IHC 2022	UCP H	Conference	Presentation	Angers	France	14-20, August 2022	Research, Industry and Policy Makers
"AI for Industry and Business" online event organized by the Hellenic Federation of Enterprises	https://tinyurl.com/mrmy5s3	SCiO	Industry event	Presentation	virtual	virtual	23-03-2022	Industry

4 ASSESSMENT OF D&C ACTIVITIES

As already mentioned the GOhydro D&C plan includes not just the enlisting of the various activities, but also a form of self-assessment through monitoring of specific KPI. Table 2 presents in a cohesive and succinct way the targeted KPIs per action both for Year 1 and Year 2, the achieved values and a color-coded self-assessment. The values for Year 1 are slightly modified with respect to the 1st version of D5.3, since more related data were gathered after the submission of the deliverable. The color-coded self-assessment is as follows:

- **Blue** color indicates the KPIs that were not just achieved, but the KPIs were achieved even at the end of Year 1 and in some cases surpassing the cumulative target KPI values.
- **Green** color indicates KPIs that were achieved.
- **Orange** indicates KPIs that were close to the predicted values.
- **Red** signals KPIs that were not achieved as predicted.
- An analysis follows after the Table.

Table 2 KPI values and self-assessment

KPI Code	Lead Partner	KPI Description	Year 1 Target	Year 1 Achieved Value (as of 28/02/2022)	Year 2 Target (cumulative)	Year 2 Achieved Value (as of 28/02/2023)
K1.1	Holisun	Project Website Unique Visitors	1000	336	2000	1400
K1.2	Holisun	Downloads	50	350	300	507
K1.3	Holisun	Newsletter Subscribers	100	16	200	30
K2.1	Holisun	Tweets	35	38	100	84
K2.2	Holisun	Twitter Followers	50	63	300	81
K2.3	Holisun	LinkedIn Page Members	50	128	100	153
K2.4	Holisun	Research Gate Followers	10	9	50	9
K2.5	Holisun	YouTube Videos	0	3	2	3
K3.1	Holisun	Journal Publications	1	2	4	7
K3.2	Holisun	Conference Proceedings	2	3	6	4
K4.1	Holisun	Newspaper/Magazine Articles	1	1	4	2
K4.2	Holisun	Interviews and Presentations	1	1	2	1
K5.1	Holisun	Scientific Conferences/Workshops	4	3	12	6
K5.2	Holisun	Industry Events	1	7	4	10
K5.3	NCSR-D	Number of young students attending NCSR-D educational programme in urban farming	100	150	300	150

As can be seen from Table 2 **the D&C plan was proven to be very efficient during Year 1** and led to significantly successful results in the middle of the project (more detailed analysis can be found in the Year 1 version of D5.3):

1. A quarter of the KPIs (4 out of 15 or 27%) surpassed the targeted values set for Year 1, while another 25% (4 out of 15 or 27%) even surpassed the targeted values set for the entire project duration even before Year 1
2. 2 KPIs (K2.4 Research Gate Followers and K5.1 Scientific conferences/Workshops) were very close to attaining the target values for Year 1 (9 followers instead of 10 / 3 conference participations instead of 4). The slight delay of K5.1 was mostly due to two factors (i) the current pandemic imposing during 2020 travel restrictions and several event cancellations, (ii) a delay in the national funding for two partners (SciO and NCSR) that has put a severe restriction in budget allocation, which was mostly funneled to consumables and personnel costs.
3. Only 1 KPI (K1.1 Project Website Unique Visitors) ran a moderate risk of not being fully-achieved
4. Only 1 KPI (K1.3 Newsletter Subscription) ran the risk of not being fully achieved. Again, K1.1 and K1.3 seem to be partly attributed to the COVID-19 pandemic, which had forced people to a daily overflow of digital information and hence a reduced interest in receiving additional information in an electronic format.

Based on the findings of Year 1, the D&C Plan was deemed very appropriate, since most of the KPIs had been achieved with over 50% of them successfully completed or even exceeding expectations and surpassing the targeted values foreseen for the entire duration of the project. Therefore, the consortium opted to keep the plan as it was. The delays and the general restrictions due to the COVID-19 pandemic, were interpreted as the main reasons for the few KPIs that were not being satisfactorily progressing. The self-assessment as well as the total impressions from the LinkedIn and Twitter accounts (see Annex II) also indicated at the time that the most effective **means for communication** was the **social media presence** and therefore considerable effort was put into maintain a strong presence in the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts with frequent posts. Research Gate did not produce the same results in terms of project appeal, since as a platform it is mostly dedicated to scientific publications. Research Gate is more suitable for scientific dissemination rather than a venue to promote communication activities. These –apart from the success of KPIs- was a *significant finding for the entire consortium that will be appropriately exploited and implemented in future projects.*

As was mentioned, GOhydro placed considerable effort in communicating the progress and the project results to larger audiences through its LinkedIn and Twitter Accounts. Even though the respective KPIs were set as “followers” (KPI 2.2 and KPI 2.3) and only the number of “Tweets” (KPI 2.1) were set as a KPI, it is worth taking into account in the GOhydro D&C Activities assessment the number of posts at the LinkedIn account as well as the responses generated by all posts in both social media accounts (see details in Annex II). As can be seen in Table 3 doubling the posts in LinkedIn during Year 2 and maintaining the same rate of posting in Twitter resulted in average 135 and 186 impressions per post (for the entire project duration), respectively. It can also be seen in Table 2 that LinkedIn was a better means to maintain interest with an almost steady rate of ~130 impressions per post and an increase in impressions per follower during the second year. Therefore, increasing the number of posts per month helped at creating a larger impact. On the contrary, Twitter followers who might not originate necessarily from the scientific world demonstrated a decreasing interest despite the increase in posting frequency. Taking into account the fact that the LinkedIn Followers surpassed our expectations (Table 2), *the second lesson learned from implementing the GOhydro project was that LinkedIn is the best social media-related venue to attract interest in a scientific proposal with Twitter following close in but being harder to maintain “hype” around a project.* In addition, a *third lesson learned was that better performance metric is the number of followers and the number of impressions per post.*

Table 3 Summary of Social Media Additional Metrics

	LinkedIn Posts	Twitter Posts	LinkedIn Impressions	Twitter Impressions	LinkedIn Followers	Twitter Followers
Year 1	21	38	2865	10240	128	63
Year 2	42	46	5685	5138	153	81
Total	63	84	8550	15378	281	144
Year 1 Average	2 posts/m onth*	3 posts/m onth*	136 impressions/post	163 impressions/post	22 impressions/follower	163 impressions/follower
Year 2 Average	4 posts/m onth*	4 posts/m onth*	124 impressions/post	63 impressions/post	37 impressions/follower	63 impressions/follower

* the average was calculated assuming 11 working months per year

Returning to Table 2 and the self-assessment of the D&C activities, the results were quite satisfactory but not according to the projections given the very promising results of Year 1. In more detail:

1. Five KPIs (33%) *surpassed by far the targeted values*. This was particularly important in terms of Dissemination of Scientific results in the form of Journal publications (KPI 3.1) and Industry Events (KPI 5.2) which speak highly for the actual implementation of the project and the importance of its results. The other KPIs are strong indicators showing the efficacy of specific venues of communication.
2. Only two KPIs (13%) were not achieved with values considerably lower than anticipated. These were the Research Gate Followers (KPI 2.4) and the Newsletter Subscribers (KPI 1.3). These two KPIs underperformed even at Year 1. The absence of interest for electronic subscription can be explained by the overflow of electronic material people have been “bombarded” with during and after the pandemic. The consortium believes –also judging from themselves- that over-abundance of digital information in form of e-mails is not seen favorably any more. Instead, there is a general tendency for people to get quickly informed through short but informative social media posts. This was also verified by the number of LinkedIn followers that surpassed the targeted values and the fact they maintained an almost steady interest throughout the 2 years of the project. On the contrary, Research Gate did not attract the same amount of interest (very few followers), since it has become over the years a platform for scientific questions/answers and getting information about scientific publications. Most probably a most appropriate metric would have been the views of articles published throughout the project and by the RG interest of the key researchers of the project.
3. The remaining KPIs were partially (25%) or almost achieved (25%). The KPIs related to conferences/workshops/schools (and in general D&C activities that required physical presence) were restricted severely by two factors: (i) the COVID-19 pandemic imposing travel restrictions and several event cancellations for more than half of the project duration, (ii) a delay in the national funding for two partners (SciO and NCSR) that has put a severe restriction in budget allocation, which was mostly funneled to consumables and personnel costs in order to produce the deliverables of the project. The 2 KPIs (Twitter followers and Tweets) have been already analyzed above. KPI 1.1 (Unique website visitors) is still considered successful by the consortium even though it did not reach the target value (1400 instead of 2000). This KPI is considered a success since the GOhydro project managed to *quadruple its* visitors after Year 1 and the actual generation of hard scientific results. Finally, with regards to KPI 4.2 (Magazine/Newspaper Articles) again, this was a partial success (2 articles instead of 4), but the exact reasons for not attracting press interest was not entirely clear to the consortium (possibly there is a need for stronger networking of the host institutions with the press and not just scientific networking).

5 CONCLUSIONS

The D&C plan has proven to be very efficient and well laid out. The plan was successfully implemented and several of the KPIs have not only been achieved but already surpassed the targeted values for the entire project duration. Partial achievement of some of the KPIs were mostly related to the COVID-19 pandemic and could not have been anticipated.

An added benefit of the self-assessment analysis, which was not originally planned in the project, but constitutes an initiative of the GOhydro consortium, has helped in drawing several useful conclusions and several lessons were learned about the efficacy of D&C venues and the setting of meaningful KPIs. These lessons were valuable and will be implemented by all partners in future projects.

ANNEX I-GOHYDRO LEAFLET

ICT-AGRI-FOOD Topic 1: Data-driven ICT platforms and solutions to improve the sustainability of agrifood Systems

Horizon 2020

GOHYDRO

A SMART-SENSING AI-DRIVEN PLATFORM FOR SCALABLE, LOW-COST HYDROPONIC UNITS

The main motivation for the GOHYDRO project is the optimization of the cultivation process that will allow the harvest of the best possible products in any hydroponic installation including low-cost, consumer-grade equipment. To achieve this, a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring the crops' health and nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated microgreens will be developed. The platform will integrate different sensor kits for nutrient, plant health and environment monitoring for indoor production of various microgreens. The main output of the project will be an e-agronomist for hydroponic growers, helping them to make informed decisions for the production of high yields of nutrient-dense microgreens.

BACKGROUND

One of the biggest challenges of humanity in the 21st century is to devise sustainable solutions to produce more food while minimizing environmental impact. Hydroponics has emerged as one such solution, as it requires no arable land, reduces the usage of clean water and can be used in any urban setting. Within this framework, GOHYDRO aims at developing a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring the crops' health and nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated microgreens in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow the harvest of the best possible products.

GOHYDRO aspires to culminate in the production of a platform that will be a shifting paradigm of how AI-driven technological innovation can become an affordable, accessible-by-all tool applicable to all forms of urban farming. In a nutshell, the proposal aims at creating a form of an easy-to-use e-agronomist which will assist any grower to fine-tune and optimize her hydroponic production.

MAIN PROJECT ACTIVITIES

GOHYDRO platform will be based on the merging of two innovative tools:

- a new type of fully-immersible, microfluidic-free silicon photonic probes capable of effortless on-the-spot spectral recording of microgreen pulps and
- an artificial intelligence (AI) component implementing a multi-model approach that will produce accurate predictions and recommendations with limited amounts of data.

The main project activities can be summarised as follows:

- Thorough review and analysis of the factors that affect microgreens growth and nutrient quality, in terms of nutritional and environmental requirements as well as lighting needs of the plants.
- Selection of sundry sensing devices to be included in the platform as a Multi-modal sensor kit, and the subsequent definition of multiple climate recipes, i.e. environmental and nutrient configurations to be checked for optimising the cultivation of microgreens.
- Evaluation cycles of incremental proximity to the realistic usage of the platform, i.e., as a stand-alone hydroponic unit installable in everyday settings and requiring no expertise to be managed and configured.

EXPECTED SOCIAL IMPACT

The societal benefits of the project outputs are adding value to the living spaces and working environments with plants for healthy eating habits, profitable and aesthetically pleasing exploitation of vacant spaces and abandoned buildings in the city. In addition, the system can be also used as a demonstrator farm in schools and kindergartens promoting sustainable solutions for the new generations, in community farms for elders and close-knit communities sharing kitchen and other living spaces, as a teaching platform to promote microgreens as an essential element of healthy dietary habits and hydroponics as a new "currency" for quality of life in urban settings, or even as a teaching platform in disaster areas and refugee camps for food production.

Keywords

- Microgreens
- Urban farming
- Smart sensors
- Data-driven platform
- Hydroponic units
- Machine learning

Duration

01/03/2021 - 28/02/2023

TRL

Technology Readiness Level 7

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- MEF, Denmark
- BMEL, Germany
- EUFISCDI, Romania

ANNEX II–LIST OF POSTS IN SOCIAL MEDIA AND THEIR IMPRESSIONS

#	Publish Date	Tweet URL	Total Impressions (Twitter)	Lead Partner
1	18.03.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1372532610505834501	384	SCiO
2	18.03.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1372501315570569217	939	SCiO
3	24.03.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1374736454585356292	795	SCiO
4	08.07.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1413012070476492804	476	Holisun
5	12.07.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1414538047006380034	384	Holisun
6	19.07.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1417089792022618115	149	UCPH
7	26.07.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1419587412565676034	189	Holisun
8	02.08.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1422083519329734660	141	NCSR-D
9	03.08.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/142245628835785265	395	NCSR-D
10	16.08.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1427171305749688322	142	USAMV
11	17.08.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1427518276788269057	139	nr21 DESIGN
12	23.08.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1429691667318181888	427	SCiO
13	30.08.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1432210711917248512	143	UCPH
14	06.09.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1434778868540452865	261	SCiO
15	13.09.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1437361447688884224	247	SCiO
16	20.09.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1439921344674738176	331	SCiO
17	27.09.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1442443751008477186	291	USAMV
18	28.09.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1442762477419343872	105	USAMV
19	04.10.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1444943686085844993	182	Holisun
20	11.10.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1447454872966664193	519	Holisun
21	18.10.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1449973646412353538	284	Holisun
22	25.10.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1452527691333263366	174	Holisun
23	01.11.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1455163753276784641	321	SCiO
24	08.11.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1457688695633551361	759	Holisun
25	15.11.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1460190119575662597	190	Holisun

26	23.11.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1463050314760830979	259	Holisun
27	29.11.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1465307684471779330	210	Holisun
28	14.11.2021	https://twitter.com/rusu_teodor/status/1448705887179313152	189	USAMV
29	06.12.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1467750826307379200	202	Holisun
30	07.12.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1468214547492356106	69	NCSR-D
31	13.12.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1470374924082724869	267	Holisun
32	21.12.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1473184953819144192	54	Holisun
33	24.12.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1474258538675462153	74	Holisun
34	31.12.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1476825451393961990	142	Holisun
35	03.01.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1477957919832485890	132	Holisun
36	17.01.2021	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1483023373177348100	63	Holisun
37	09.02.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/149132119382859779	16	Holisun
38	15.02.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1493491141366493186	15	SCiO
39	21.02.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1495742864332103685	236	SCiO
40	07.03.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1500736922649604097	286	nr21 DESIGN
41	14.03.2022	https://twitter.com/ictagrifood/status/1503394731606347777		Holisun
42	16.03.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1504090426759864321	59	Holisun
43	28.03.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1508350281083494402	130	nr21 DESIGN
44	04.04.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1510953870507270146	184	Holisun
45	04.05.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1521727498123464705	132	USAMV
46	04.05.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1521746597033521152	263	Holisun
47	17.05.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1526456662344847361	335	UCPH
48	24.05.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1529066599189295105	122	Holisun
49	25.05.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1529419695564238849	97	nr21 DESIGN
50	03.06.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1532676960538742785	132	UCPH
51	06.06.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1533740520274595840	191	UCPH
52	08.06.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1534432947729846274	294	USAMV
53	15.06.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1536991192679866368	84	nr21 DESIGN
54	20.06.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1538783709507330048	208	UCPH
55	05.07.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1544194783547203585	144	UCPH
56	11.07.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1546384924835516416	170	Holisun
57	12.07.2022	https://twitter.com/ictagrifood/status/1546806612001693697		Holisun

58	18.07.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1548933095927283712	222	Holisun
59	25.07.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1551477381541642247	236	Holisun
60	25.07.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1551479351778201600	119	Holisun
61	09.09.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1568202793084719104	135	SCiO
62	12.09.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1569193269594304512	99	Holisun
63	20.09.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1572184627124797440	119	NCSR-D
64	28.09.2022	https://twitter.com/ictagrifood/status/1575106827590971403		SCiO
65	28.09.2022	https://twitter.com/SCiO_systems/status/1575039390581403648		SCiO
66	05.10.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1577579517601878016	107	SCiO
67	19.10.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1582617552316170240	68	USAMV
68	21.10.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1583337788199489536	110	USAMV
69	4.11.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1588533350264078336	42	nr21 DESIGN
70	9.11.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1590267081353998337	122	USAMV
71	17.11.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1593137371884707840	113	USAMV
72	21.11.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1594579361331560449	94	USAMV
73	23.11.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1595391789183238146	45	USAMV
74	25.11.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1596026899402063872	78	SCiO
75	25.11.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1596088251861073922	40	Holisun
76	6.12.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1600101862388006913	81	UCPH
77	6.12.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1600104073285357574	29	UCPH
78	8.12.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1600737690193825794	33	Holisun
79	13.12.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1602654359548051456	43	USAMV
80	15.12.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1603328555030663179	136	USAMV
81	20.12.2022	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1605106318506971137	36	USAMV
82	8.2.2023	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1623300618101178369	125	Holisun
83	9.2.2023	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1623586901146931202	86	Holisun
84	27.2.2023	https://twitter.com/gohydroeu/status/1630097309475262464	21	Holisun
Total Twitter Impressions:			15378	

#	Publish Date	Linkedin URL	Total Impressions (LinkedIn)	Lead Partner
1	24.03.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6780500902475284481	115	SciO
2	30.08.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6840238049050419200	63	UCPH
3	06.09.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6840545533136920576	76	SciO
4	13.09.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6842739490906267648	65	SciO
5	20.09.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6845687219420839936	233	SciO
6	27.09.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6848218619667738624	79	USAMV
7	28.09.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6848528761122631680	51	USAMV
8	04.10.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6851106182204153856	76	Holisun
9	11.10.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6853221742270394368	94	Holisun
10	18.10.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6855777413083860992	53	Holisun
11	25.10.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6858300522236116993	169	Holisun
12	01.11.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6860930333551022080	259	SciO
13	08.11.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6863477194992304128	158	Holisun
14	15.11.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6865958632652177408	123	Holisun
15	23.11.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6868816860251602944	159	Holisun
16	29.11.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6871074057627037696	206	Holisun
18	06.12.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6897087148856553472	48	
17	07.12.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6899257020571017216	67	Holisun
18	13.12.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6901508890060500992	71	NCSR-D
19	21.12.2021	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6906502886386151424	128	Holisun
20	09.02.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6897087148856553472	47	Holisun
21	15.02.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6899257020571017216	104	SciO
22	21.02.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6901508890060500992	240	SciO
23	07.03.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6906502886386151424	181	nr21 DESIGN
24	09.02.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6897087148856553472	47	Holisun
25	16.03.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6909855433616719873	164	Holisun
26	28.03.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6914116119343583233	104	nr21 DESIGN
27	04.04.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6916719836211392513	278	Holisun

28	04.05.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6927494399148847104	116	USAMV
29	04.05.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6927512644631298048	149	Holisun
30	17.05.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6932222514446094336	281	UCPH
31	24.05.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6934832550817214464	98	Holisun
32	25.05.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6935185472444846080	130	nr21 DESIGN
33	03.06.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6938442897885147136	49	UCPH
34	06.06.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6939506506480381952	161	UCPH
35	08.06.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6940199375318982656	77	USAMV
36	15.06.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6942757007552569344	110	nr21 DESIGN
37	05.07.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6949960819455451136	70	UCPH
38	11.07.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6952150765243117568	90	Holisun
39	18.07.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6954699213385392128	418	Holisun
40	25.07.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6957243855637221376	253	Holisun
41	25.07.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6957245116587651072	92	Holisun
42	09.09.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6973969747268788224	27	SCiO
43	12.09.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6974959571584839682	58	Holisun
44	20.09.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/gohydro_so-excited-that-our-work-konstantinos-misiakos-activity-6957661781951438848-OVVD?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	57	NCSR-D
45	05.10.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6983345415626592256	301	SCiO
46	19.10.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6988384319803154433	223	USAMV
47	21.10.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6989108255113273344	430	USAMV
48	4.11.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6994299224519512064	251	nr21 DESIGN
49	9.11.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6996033353778913280	197	USAMV
50	17.11.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6998906237283102721	149	USAMV
51	21.11.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7000384960171790336	175	USAMV
52	23.11.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7001157244356595712	226	USAMV
53	25.11.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7001797250775437312	247	SCiO
54	25.11.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7001854286586392576	101	Holisun
55	6.12.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7005869406836666368	122	UCPH
56	6.12.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:700587009977634304	103	UCPH
57	8.12.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7036603375718666241	91	Holisun

58	13.12.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7008420651698950144	141	USAMV
59	15.12.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7009094442146017280	146	USAMV
60	20.12.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7010872522514546688	166	USAMV
61	8.2.2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7029066502867726336	118	Holisun
62	9.2.2023	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7029352825214091264	86	Holisun
63	05.10.2022	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7035863241826217984	92	Holisun
Total LinkedIn Impressions			850	